

MODERNIZATION OF THE SYSTEM FOR PREPARING PHYSICAL EDUCATION SPECIALISTS FOR PROFESSIONAL CAREER ACTIVITIES

Xolboeva Gulxayo Xolboevna

O'zbekiston-Finlandiya pedagogika instituti DSc, v.b.professor

E-mail: Gulxayoxolboyevna482@gmail.com

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Abstract: Like any area of the social sphere, physical education and sports require financial costs, but through the social influence obtained, it covers the costs spent on production in the field of sports many times. Physical education and sports expenses-this is the investment in human health, which determines the quality of the country's labor resources. However, today the effectiveness of the physical education system and the sphere that constitutes it requires a lot of processes. The functioning and further development of the field of "Physical Culture "in the conditions of a modern market economy involves the constant search for additional sources of financing, innovative means of competitive struggle, market relations.

Keywords: career, HARD and SOFT skills, specialist, student, model, intellectualism, profiling, trend, creativity, professional potential.

МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ПОДГОТОВКИ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ К ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация: Как и любая область социальной сферы, физическая культура и спорт требуют финансовых затрат, но за счет получаемого социального влияния многократно перекрываются затраты, затраченные на производство продукции в сфере спорта. Расходы на физкультуру и спорт — это инвестиции в здоровье человека, определяющие качество трудовых ресурсов страны. Однако сегодня для эффективности системы физического воспитания и сферы, ее составляющей, необходимо множество процессов. Функционирование и дальнейшее развитие направления «Физическая культура» в условиях современной рыночной экономики предполагает постоянный поиск дополнительных источников финансирования, инновационных средств конкурентной борьбы, рыночных отношений.

Ключевые слова: карьера, HARD и SOFT навыки, специалист, студент, модель, интеллектуализм, профилирование, тренд, креативность, профессиональный потенциал.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, like in all sectors, practical efforts are being made to train physical education and sports specialists by studying international experiences and preparing them to compete at the level of developed countries. "Research and innovation activities in education are carried out with the aim of modernizing education, and tasks such as developing new educational technologies and resources, testing them, and integrating them into the educational process" have been set. In recent years, social research conducted among the leaders and specialists of sports organizations confirms that the demand for organizational, professional, and career-oriented skills for physical education and sports specialists is increasing. Future specialists are expected to be self-reliant but also ready for result-oriented activities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of studying the professional and career readiness of students in higher education institutions specializing in physical education and sports based on a competency-based approach is

reflected in the works of K.D. Yarashev, N.A. Muslimov, S.S. Sharipov, G.S. Nasriddinova, and others. The professionals of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) have also addressed the career and professional issues of students in physical education and sports higher education institutions. The works of S.V. Gusev, M.A. Kuznetsova, V.N. Smirnov, N.V. Andreeva, I.P. Morozova focus on controversial issues such as defining the professional career status and career trends, their essence, and structure. T.V. Yakovleva and O.V. Kovalenko analyze the system of professional development for specialists in physical culture, methods for effectively organizing it, enhancing specialists' professional competencies, and supporting their career growth, providing evidence of the effectiveness of their recommendations through experimental practices.

Research Aim The aim of the research is to develop proposals and recommendations for modernizing the system of preparing future physical education specialists for professional and career activities.

Research Objectives

1. Improve the technical process of shaping professional-career competencies through the professional development of future physical education specialists.
2. Expand the opportunities for modernizing the unified educational process in line with the trends in the development of the physical education system.
3. Strengthen the motivation of future professionals in physical education and sports to achieve continuous professional growth.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research methods employed include theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific-methodical literature, analysis of educational process documents, pedagogical observations, surveys, analysis of physical and morphofunctional indicators using "TANITA-BIOIMPEDANCE" and "SPIROGRAPH" devices, methods for identifying pedagogical competencies, testing intellectual abilities through pedagogical tests, and statistical analysis methods.

Scientific Novelty The scientific novelty of the research lies in the development of a multidisciplinary approach to the application of exercises designed to select and develop the components of the structural links or joints that ensure the compatibility of the necessary morphofunctional system for achieving professional career success. This approach enhances the deep acquisition of practical reflective skills.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methods include theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific-methodical literature, pedagogical experience, analysis of educational process documents, pedagogical observations, surveys, methods to identify management skills, intellectual ability structure testing, sociological analysis, and mathematical statistics.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This study provides insights into the dynamics of the students' relationship with their future professional competencies, the planning of career-related intellectual indicators, and the issues surrounding the implementation of pedagogical competencies during their educational activities. The dynamic changes in students' attitudes towards their professional careers have been analyzed throughout the research.

Table 1. Dynamics of Changes in the Relationship of Students to Professional Activities in the Experimental and Control Groups (n=80)

Personal Traits	TG ($\pm\sigma$)	Reliability of Differences (P)	NG ($\pm\sigma$)	Reliability of Differences (P)
Career Interest Stability	3.2 \pm 1.8	<0.01	3.1 \pm 1.4	<0.05
Career Inclination	3.2 \pm 0.9	<0.01	2.8 \pm 1.3	>0.05
Career Interest	7.6 \pm 1.9	<0.05	7.6 \pm 2.5	>0.05
Intellectual Component	7.3 \pm 1.8	<0.05	8.0 \pm 1.8	>0.05
Emotional Component	6.4 \pm 3.3	<0.001	6.5 \pm 2.0	>0.05
Volitional Component	8.4 \pm 3.0	>0.05	3.1 \pm 1.4	<0.05

TG – Experimental group, NG – Control group, TB – beginning of the experiment, TO – end of the experiment

The analysis of the dynamic changes in the relationship of students in both the experimental and control groups to their professional activities revealed the following results:

- **Career interest stability** improved in the experimental group from 3.2 at the start of the study to 4.1 by the end, while the control group saw an increase from 3.1 to 3.9.
- **Career inclination** increased in the experimental group from 3.2 to 4.0, whereas the control group had a slight increase from 2.8 to 3.5.

Table 2. Distribution of Career Interest Stability Among Experimental Participants (%)

Group	Experimental Phase	Career Attitude	Interest	Sufficiently Stable Interest	Unstable Interest
Experimental	Initial	38.1	48.2	13.1	
	Final	45.6	51.8	2.6	
Control	Initial	38.0	46.3	15.7	
	Final	40.1	48.0	11.9	

At the initial stage, **38.4%** of the experimental participants and **37.0%** of the control group exhibited stable career interest. The second group displayed insufficient satisfaction with their chosen profession, as well as an unclear attitude towards their profession, along with a lack of sufficient cognitive activity in pursuing the profession. This group comprised **48.3%** of the experimental group and **48%** of the control group.

Table 3. General Physical Fitness Indicators of Experimental and Control Group Participants during the Study (n=40)

Test No.	Control Tests	Start of Study	End of Study	t	P
1. 60m Running (seconds)	TG	11.44	11.10	3.74	<0.001
	NG	11.49	11.41	0.69	>0.5
2. Chin-ups (times)	TG	4.82	7.42	2.06	<0.05

	NG	4.75	5.30	0.78	<0.05
3. Push-ups from a prone position (times)	TG	18.41	23.11	2.91	<0.01
	NG	18.59	20.23	1.71	<0.1
4. Standing Long Jump (cm)	TG	160.24	185.4	2.11	<0.05
	NG	159.92	165.8	0.70	>0.5

TG – Experimental Group, **NG** – Control Group

The table presents the physical fitness indicators of participants in both groups. The data shows improvements in the experimental group in multiple areas, such as in running, chin-ups, push-ups, and long jumping, which are attributed to the new methodologies used in the physical education program. The experimental group experienced significant improvements, while the control group had smaller or no changes.

This study demonstrates that the use of innovative methods in physical education, such as integrating new training techniques, creating a healthy lifestyle, and motivating students, can lead to positive changes in physical readiness. The application of technologies, digitization, and collaboration with external partners also enhances learning, and tools such as mobile apps provide students with real-time feedback, allowing them to analyze their physical progress more effectively.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The modernization of the system for preparing physical education specialists through pedagogical and methodological innovations, multidisciplinary approaches, and the use of modern technologies significantly improves their professional and career skills. The changes implemented in physical education, including individualization, virtual learning programs, and the development of sports techniques, have contributed to improving the practical skills of students and specialists. As a result, students have developed essential knowledge and skills to succeed in their professional careers in physical education and sports. Furthermore, their leadership, creativity, and professional communication abilities have also significantly improved, demonstrating that the physical education system has been modernized to meet the current social and economic needs.

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